

ANALYSIS OF THE NOVEL "LIVES LAST IN A DREAM".

Annotation: The writer glorified the national characteristics of the Uzbek people, such as humanity, honesty, purity, hard work, and patriotism, which are contained in the mind and spirit of the people, and revealed vices such as injustice, corruption, impurity, and intelligence. The work has a unique structure. It contains clips from Rustam's diary

Key Words: Novel, era, image, writer, analysis.

Life in the 80s of the 20th century is skillfully depicted in O'zbek Rushidov's novel "Late Lives in a Dream". Transparency and critical spirit are strong in the work. The writer glorified the national characteristics of the Uzbek people, such as humanity, honesty, purity, hard work, and patriotism, which are contained in the mind and psyche of the people, and revealed such vices as injustice, corruption, impurity, and intelligence. The work has a unique structure. It contains clips from Rustam's diary. In the novel, one of the heroes of the work, Rustam, quits his studies and goes to the army, and from the army he is sent to Afghanistan, where the war is going on. He does not fight for the Motherland and its people, but for the political interests of the Soviet government, which is the invasion. He witnesses young men like him dying for nothing in Afghanistan, who are suffering greatly from the Afghan war. He gets sick as a result of the war. He cannot get rid of the memories of the Afghan war.

Even though he is married to his beloved daughter Shabnosa, they cannot be happy. The main reason for his misfortune was the negative impact of the war. This incident

every reader. He followed in his father's footsteps and became a Soviet communist. In his youth, he caused many people to be unjustly punished. Aunt Qurbaniy does not know what she spent her life on. Even if his health deteriorates and he is unable to work, he does not stop doing homework. Even if the doctors are not allowed, they are busy with their daily worries. This woman's life was as meaningless and miserable as in a dream.

The question of the hero and his psyche is one of the last issues for the full manifestation of the work of art. The events of O'zbek Rushidov's novel "Late Lives in a Dream" begin by giving an image of autumn. The artistic skill of the creator is also seen in the fact that he starts the events with the allegory "...autumn is like a patient lying on the draftbed..." and mentally prepares the reader for the tragic situation that will happen later.

The events of "Uzbek work" and "winter work" are skillfully described in the novel. The work depicts the image of honest Uzbek farmers who suffered from the oppression of paratroopers-investigators who came from Moscow to Uzbekistan to "bring justice". The image of Rustam's father, the innocent "gully" Shommaron Shommarov, is a living proof of this. He is embodied in the novel as a master gardener, a humble person who worked honestly and lived honestly all his life. Arrested and humiliated by paratroopers without reason, the grandfather of the chairman leaves an unforgettable impression on the reader as a good family head and a living father.

In this novel, the author tries to preserve their national flame in the depiction of events. At the heart of the events of the work there are significant generalizations, deep thoughts that express the important aspects of people's lives. First of all, the author skillfully points the scenes of the human personality and his spiritual world. Secondly, it condemns the so-called disaster, reveals its inhuman nature.

Through the novel "Tashkent kishoniyatida", the writer showed what upheavals were expected in the human psyche as a result of the war. For example, in the scene of Rustam and Shakhmurov's wedding at their neighbor's house in Qashqad, the spiritual qualities characteristic of the Uzbek nation are not left behind in terms of the scope and depth of the manifestations of the qualities of the previous novels. In the wedding episode in the novel, basic moral qualities such as characterfulness and conscience appear as national symbols. The image of hundreds of people silently leaving their heads in front of the carelessness of a single stranger, heartlessness, was a vivid proof of Uzbekistan's success in raising sheep-people.

It is known to us that thousands of children of the Uzbek nation were sacrificed in the storms of the war and the tyranny of the authoritarian regime. Qurbani is the biggest victim of this period and regime in the play. Qurbani is like a symbol of Uzbek women.

In her, the attitude, kindness, faith, and purity characteristic of real Uzbek women have been preserved. True, his name is mentioned in one place of the work. This happens during the search of a letter written to a Japanese resident in the house of the victims, while the Commissioner is carrying

another "clean-up".

"Thank the sacrifice! Did you find it, about your daughter? No, he was born on Eid al-Adha. You are a teacher at school, you read Quran at home... Sucker! Hypocrite! The girl was still hugging her mother, apparently she wanted to fly to her father and hang on his neck, but she was afraid of the unknown "sucker".

At this point, the intention of the writer to choose the name Qurbani only to show the attitude towards religion and religious ceremonies at that time seems a little far from the truth. In my opinion, the image of Qurbani is embodied in the play as the greatest victim of the war. However, since he was a child, he saw a lot of political violence, and he was separated from his grandfather, father, and finally his mother. These events and scenes took away his heart. That's why he accepted fate and was a son of God.

The person who destroyed the whole life and youth of Commissioner Qurbani. His father imprisons brother To'lagan with children. His mother, Fatima, was also debauched and took her life. But Qurbani does not respond to any of them. He gives everything to God. The commissar, the manager of the Soviet government, lives his whole life to build communism. He does not trust anyone, not even his children, his wife, his loved ones. The writer clearly proves his appearance. Although the times and society change, this person remains unchanged. As a result, she loses her children. At this point, I found it necessary to quote Qurbani.

"Do you know who is the wisest people in the world?" Australian Aboriginals! He does not imprison a person who commits a serious or

a person who commits a serious crime. Does not shoot, does not hang. He leaves alive. One cell. It's been more than ten years since the commissar has been alone... Alone?"

Utkin Hashimov portrays the image of Sait Gasiyev and shows the actions of this commissar. He adds his worthy "contribution" in the imprisonment of his friend Talygan, who grew up playing in the same neighborhood. After arresting him, he violated the home of his wife Fatima and left his daughter Qurbany as orphan.

Aldi emphasizes that our nation has reached such a decline in spirituality. Sait Gasiyev's disbelief is to such an extent that he even finds and tears up the holy book of the Muslim world, the Holy Qur'an. Leadership is for the commissar, a weapon of revenge against the enemies, he will do what he wants. But he shows his true face with his evil deeds.

The biography in the novel mentions the commissar's unreliability and his "incompatible" services to the Soviet government. Even though the commissar has reached the end of his life, he did not develop as a person during his life, but lived as a "special person" of the Soviet ideology. Its outcome has already come. But the Commissar is so confused that he does not want to admit this fact. In hindsight, everyone left him. A woman like Navira, that is, his wife, children, daughters-in-law turned away from him. He was not faithful to his next wife. Not a friend, not a supporter left. In the end, the society and ideology that he believed in collapsed. However, he lacks the understanding of this very fact. Because he had completely turned into an animal in human form, a creature devoid of any human feelings.

In the image of Commissar Sait Gasiyev, the oppression and injustice of the era of the end of personality is clearly exposed. Sait Gasiyev is a black head, an evil person, and a collective image of the NKVD officers who oppressed the people.

There is no creature that is not born of a mother. With the exception of Adam, Eve, and Aazel, who were cast out of Paradise, a mother gave birth to all creatures. As stated in the hadiths, every child is born a Muslim. But as he grows up, his religion and character may change. It depends on the environment, upbringing in the environment. Unfortunately, such commissars were also born by one mother. The watch was also given life by a single mother. However, under the influence of the environment, they all accepted the curse. We can see this in the case of the commissars.

Said Ahmad says about the novel "Life in a Dream": "I will not tell the events of the novel. Readers know this better than I do. I just want to emphasize that our writer is saddened by the grief of the people and sympathizes with their pain.

The novel cannot be read without excitement. It shocks the reader. He enters from the bottom of his heart to the crazy warmongers who started a bloody war that brought nothing but death upon the people."

The interpretation of war in the novel is completely new. Unlike previous war stories, here there is no division of opposing forces into friends and enemies, black and white. There are no winners and losers, heroes and traitors, there are only innocent people who are victims of war, the social system of that time, ideological differences, and competition.

War is destruction for both sides, death, separation, calamity, wound in body and soul, terrible tragedy!

The writer was able to use the motifs of dreams in the work directly in connection with the title of the work. He does not tell the future events in detail, but instead uses dream episodes. Through Rustam's dream, the reader realizes that his father is unjustly accused:

"I had a strange dream. My father is lying on his bed in the yard. There is no blanket under him, he is lying on a dry floor. Dad doesn't say a word when I tell him to give me a blanket. Nisgal cries. I have never seen my father cry. I was scared. When I ran to him, my father disappeared."

Another dream episode hints at Rustam's death. Rustam's death is also evident in Shabnam's dream. A day before Rustam's death, he goes to his grandmother's house due to a family dispute. On this day he dreams:

"The river cracks... No, it's not a river, it's an anchor. Anchor is Gapsin Park. I was sitting on one bench, under one rug. I saw my brother Rustam standing on the other side of the water. They are laughing and looking in each other. "I don't know how to swim!" When I said, they didn't take off their clothes and threw their heads in the ditch... If I look like this... If I look...

- I looked, there is no water in the sea, no water... Blood is flowing... Brother Rustam is flowing in blood..." Adib refers to the bloody events in Rustam's life through Shabnam's dream. It can be seen that every pictorial scene used by the writer served to reveal the main purpose of the work.

Özile Hattinçer, as a true child of the Urubek people, revealed the roots of the grave tragedy that befell our nation. Most importantly, he did it skillfully.

Why is the work called "Lütfen, passed in a dream"? While thinking about this question, I found the answer in the following sentence: "When I think about it, my past life is not a dream, but a dream. It was as if someone had taken sleeping pills and I was dreaming without realizing it. Sometimes I had a sweet dream, sometimes a dangerous one, and I followed wherever that someone dragged me. I obeyed whatever he ordered. I was afraid to wake up. Now when I wake up and look around, there are many people like me." In this passage, after the injustice done to him, Shabnam opened his eyes and realized, even if it was too late, that his life was built on a lie. That's why their lives were called "Dream Lives".

In short, nothing in a person's life is in vain, even dreams seen in sleep. It is not an exaggeration to say that a dream is a sign that calls the human soul to the divine, or informs about the future, or the past.

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INFLUENCE OF OTKIR HADJIMOV'S WORKS ON LIBRARY PSYCHOLOGY

Abstract: Regardless of the conditions of time and era, the concepts of human dignity have been preserved. After reading this book, which expresses the fate of people who, even after losing a child who is connected to the fate of the country, was able to create another reason for himself that could bring joy to his heart, who were subjected to the resistance of war while trying to decorate his life with feelings of love, for our peaceful and prosperous life and happiness today. we thank you.

Key words: literature, novel, reader, psychology, method.

Said Ahmed writes in his work "What I lost and what I found": "It is unnecessary to talk about what books Otkir wrote. They became the property of Uzbek and related nations.

Even so, it would be unfair not to mention the works of this talented writer. Stories and novels such as "Spring will not return", "Listen to your heart", "There is light, there is a shadow", "Works of the world", "Between two doors", "Lives spent in a dream", "Two lives live in five", more than a hundred "Dilbar stories have become very popular among the people."

Otkir Hadjimov's novels were liked by readers with the novelty of the subject, the new interpretation of life events, the vividness of the characters, the interesting plot, the fluidity of the style, and the figurativeness of the language.

It is instructive that Otkir Hadjimov, contrary to the requirements of social realism, went the way of portraying life without any embellishment in

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his novels and achieved a serious achievement.

Otkir Hadjimov's novel "Between Two Doors" is considered one of the most significant works of the writer. The novel describes the virtues of the Uzbek people, their generosity, never losing their faith in any situation, kindness, and deep feelings. In the work, the writer skillfully wrote down the life, fate, and complications of the Uzbek people during the war, as examples of a number of complex and complicated destinies spanning a period of almost forty years. Regardless of the conditions of time and period, it has preserved the concepts of human dignity. After reading this work, which expresses the fate of people who, even when they lose their child who is connected to the fate of the country, can create another reason for themselves that can bring joy to their hearts, who are subject to the judgment of war while trying to decorate their lives with feelings of love, for our peaceful and prosperous life and happiness today. we thank you.

The work is close to the hearts in this aspect. The work depicts the fate of the people who have faced the endless sufferings of the times, who have not lost their human dignity, and the fate of the people who connected their fate with the fate of the Motherland. The reader who has read the work will witness that the creator was able to fully embody the spirit of that time in the work.

The novel "Between Two Doors" was written in 1986. Every episode convinces the reader and has a serious impact on the heart, as the professional writer deeply studied the events of the novel. The scenes of life, interpersonal relationships, their dialogues, as well as the author's own artistic style, are characterized by their naturalness and sincerity. The novel, consisting of seven parts and forty-seven chapters, is also unique in terms of its compositional structure. The writer skillfully connects the stories of the nine characters who participated in the narrative of the events in it. Such a poetic method chosen for the image requires high skill from the writer, of course. Otherwise, there would have been a break in the subject chain, and the events would have been scattered. However, the novel's power of influence and internal discipline leave a good impression on the reader.

In the novel, the story takes place in one of the villages around Tashkent, mainly during the Second World War. At the same time, in the literary work, he shows existing scenes from the life of villagers before and after the war. Thus, the novel carries almost fifty years of life related to the construction of the collective farm, the war and the Tashkent earthquake.

Utkir Abduraimov creatively used the art of modeling found in classical literature. For example, Nevrot's epic "Sabot Kayyor" is the subject and composition of this work. The story of the novel consists of nine characters of different characters and categories, such as Rabiya, Kara Anoma, Husan Dama, Masallar Shommatov, Masarrar Ahyeva, Kana, Umar Zafarali, and Olimjon Komilov. In this way, they form a whole,

complete and attractive plot of the novel.

Abdi vividly describes the events of daily life, work and worries of villagers, behavior, mutual relations, and creates vivid images of people with different fates and destinies. Strong faith, pure conscience, firm religion, elder Aeil, a brave and wise woman, passionately describes the wonderful qualities of people like Kara Anoma, Husan Dama, Kamil Tahir, Rabiya, such as humanity, honesty, selflessness, and love. The heroes of the novel, no matter what hardships, injustices, hardships or tragedies they have faced in life, they still do not deviate from the right path, do not lose their faith, act with justice and reason. Because these people have a light in their hearts and a clear conscience, the writer reflects truthfully and effectively. Through this, he skillfully reveals the signs of the national character unique to Uzbek. Especially, the image of the elder Aeil gives the novel its charm.

Even when the elder Aeil was unfairly dismissed from the chairmanship of the collective farm due to the imposition of some leaders, even when he faced the news that two citizens' sons were killed in battle, he did not get confused and depressed. This demonstrated his humanity in practice. In the characters of Kara Anoma and Husan Dama, kindness, humanity, patience and kindness are strong. Although they themselves suffer, they see only good in others, and always save them around them with pleasure.

The image of women is also depicted in the work with great skill. She is especially distinguished by her character Kara Anoma. We will learn this through the part of the novel that is narrated in the language of Kara Anoma. This character is distinguished by its

kindness, tolerance and simplicity. We can easily find out her love and affection typical of Uchik mothers from the following words:

"Where are you, my child? What countries have you visited? Is he okay? Well, even if you're a fearless person, I'd love to have someone carry you on a stretcher! I was carrying it in the palm of my hand! Your father came to your path. Now at least put me in the ground with your own hands! No, I'm not crying, baby! I will not cry. Even if I cry... No, my son. You got upset when I cry. Kobia hana. My daughter's eyes are still on the door. Waiting. He is waiting for you. If there was another girl, he would feel her skin and touch one of them to see if she was there... Oh, I wish I didn't die! Am I imagining it again? Who am I, dear child, forgive your sinful mother! I know, God forbid, if you're a *machiya*, your ghost will scream. If you're alive, you'll come and take me by the collar tomorrow. You say, "What have you done, *shimokamiya*, you are my mother, you have no faith!"

Here, too, the mother considers herself a sinner, takes all the blame, if only her child would come, the whole world would be a lamp for her. In this image, the writer embodies the image of all Uchik mothers of that time. He patiently overcomes all the difficulties he faced and finds the strength to live in life. In the novel, the images of Kana and Umas, the *sakamichi*, also play an important role. In the image of Kana, the difficult fate, regret and tragedy of the loyal wife who went to the front and disloyal to her husband Shomuro and her way is revealed in a very impressive way.

In the character of Umas Zakamichi, during the war, the dirty deeds of some chairman who were blind and shadow villain in the collective farm were skillfully exposed. Kana, the wife of Kana Anzumi's brother Shomuro, betrays her husband, and the worries in her brother's family affect Kana Anzumi's life and cause many problems. She could never forgive her daughter-in-law Kana's actions: "The young, dishonest! The child's son is a strong believer! Your husband was no less than someone else! If he was lame, he would not have been able to climb over the wall and steal! Four years of blood has passed! How many flower-like youths are walking patiently, since their husbands died in the war. Couldn't you have thought about your smart boy, *Imanishiroki*?" - Kana anzumi writes in the following.

During the play, Kana's fate ends unhappily and he regrets his actions.

Anzumi Kana's six children died, and only Kinzumi was raised to adulthood. When the war started in the homeland and hard times came, he followed his only child, Kinzumi, to the war so that he would serve for the peace of the country. Someone was destined to die in a foreign country. But Anzumi Kana did not believe that her son died in the war, she lived with hope that her son would return home safely. Therefore, he did not wear black clothes in mourning for his child. In this, we recognize how priceless a mother's heart is. The heartbroken *machiya* mother said day and night: "Where are you, my child? What countries have you visited? Is he okay? It's okay, even if you're a fearless person, I'd love to have someone carry you on a stretcher!" she said, waiting for her son.

The difficulties in the life of Kara Anna do not end there. Kamsan's lover, his only child, wants to take his stepdaughter Rabiya to his brother Shamsud. It is very difficult for him to do this work, his emotions and mental state make any human heart tremble. He feels guilty in front of his son Kamsan and in front of his daughter Rabiya, and constantly begs for their forgiveness: "My heart is pounding and my head is spinning. I am delirious, with what black hair am I... Who am I, dear child, forgive your sinful mother?"

There is another female character in the novel - Rabiya. Fate did not laugh at him either. Rabiya, orphaned by her mother from a young age, grows up under the care of her father. After the death of their mother, they moved from Samarkand to Tashkent, to the village of Nopai, and began to live in the yard of a man named Shamsud. As his father is a teacher, he teaches village children. Rabiya Shamsudiy Damsud grew up as Ghandya, his wife Kara Annam Al, their son Kamsam Alia, and Kara Anna's brother Shamsudal Ala. Rabiya grows up to be an honest, handworking girl. He fell in love with Kamsan. Kamsan and Rabiya's love withered without opening a single flower. When the war started in the country, he waited for years for the return of his lover who went to war. Although it has been several years since the end of the war, he does not get tired of waiting for it faithfully. Kara Anna appreciates Rabiya's loyalty so much: "My daughter's two eyes are still on the door. Waiting. He is waiting for you. If there was another girl, he would rub her skirt and touch one of them to see if she was there. The matchmaker did not come out of some places.

He says that because he was born or born! If there is one girl, that's it."

When Kara Anna, that is, her mother, became her tailor and asked her brother Shamsud, Rabiya lost her mind: "Does she know what she is saying, mother? After all... Kamsan brother is closer to my mother than anyone else. What the hell? Poor Rabiya is helpless in the bitter fate of fate.

Not only the main characters in the novel "Between Two Doors", but episodic characters such as Abul Karim, Sister Bahar, Olyana, Samadov will remain in the reader's memory for a long time. Because there is no artificiality in the work. On the contrary, the art of persuasion is powerful. Aids convincingly describes difficult and complex issues with extraordinary ingenuity. This situation is clearly visible in the pages where Kara Anna marries her son Kamsan's lover, Rabiya, to Shamsud, Aidi's marriage to someone who lost his young daughter-in-law, and the love of Musaffar and Musarraf, whose destinies are confused.

Said Ahmad writes: "The novel paints the life of the village during the war and the years after the war, the heroism of the soldiers, the poverty of the soldiers and deprivations of the war on the shoulders of the people, who took what they could not eat into the mouths of the warriors. The day after the wedding night, you will see the hard, hard work of brides who change their wedding dresses into work clothes after sending their grooms off to battle, young children carrying a hoe instead of their father, and striped-old women who filled the ground instead of their sons. You will hear their voices, you will see their weary faces on the island of cancer."

In the novel, every event, every detail is carefully based and described in depth. The writer was able to provide the child with characteristics, character and language characteristics of a child, an old woman characteristic of an old woman, an old man characteristic of an old man, and a bride characteristic of a bride.

In short, each work of the creator can have an unlimited influence on the psychology of the reader. Importantly, the images of the work can lead the reader to a positive path. In our opinion, every work should have such a great impact.

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